

METHODOLOGY FOR CREATING AND IMPLEMENTING SOFTWARE THAT DEVELOPS STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *The content of the software that develops students' independent work activities has been improved based on the creation of the software <https://itmf-talaba.uz> based on adapting media components to the requirements of software creation (ergonomics, design, graphics), and integrating them into innovative technologies.*

Keywords: *software, independent work activity, web application, restudy, methodology, model.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the method of ensuring the independent work of students is to organize and manage their independent work activities. The formation of independent production by students in the necessary process should be carried out systematically.

In our opinion, achieving high results in this area is based on creating interest (motivation) in students to consolidate the learned educational material during the educational process, in particular during lectures and practical and seminar sessions, and on creating a desire to expand the capacity of educational information based on reading textbooks and additional literature independently. It is important to ensure that future specialists become well-rounded, knowledgeable, independent thinkers, and inquisitive professionals, and to use new pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process that encourage them to work on themselves [1,2].

We know that pedagogical technologies have great potential in creating a desire and need for independent work in students during the educational process.

By creating software that develops independent work, we can develop the following knowledge and skills in students.

development of intelligence;

development of the emotional sphere;

development of independence, autonomy;

development of motivation to work on oneself, self-improvement and self-regulation.

In today's advanced era, many platforms (for example, Hemis), search engines, and groups on Telegram channels have created ample opportunities for students to pursue independent learning.

However, in our research, we found that it is effective for students to use a single site to provide them with the opportunity to learn independently and collaborate with other students in a group, while also exercising self-control [3,4].

The simplicity of our web application interface, which helps us organize independent learning through innovative technologies, also contributes to the effectiveness of the quality of education, as reflected in questionnaires, surveys, and tests.

Our web application, <https://itmf-talaba.uz>, has been developed to meet methodological, didactic, psychological and technical requirements, while also providing independent learning that is flexible and objectively assesses the student's level of knowledge, and has a continuous sequence that is easily integrated into various systems. This software serves to develop students' independent work activities.

A methodology for creating and implementing software that develops students' independent work activities

WEB AND MOBILE APPLICATION MAP

When creating this software, we focused on properly organizing students' independent work activities, providing positive support to students in their classroom and extracurricular activities, and helping them to fully and clearly master subject-related topics [5,6].

This site contains subjects based on the educational field, and includes information that fully covers the essence of the content of these subjects. They consist of "Lectures", "Practical Exercises" and "Independent Work", as well as "Video" and "Topic Tests", which are reflected in the following menus.

The student can fully master the topics of the subject through this module. After mastering each topic, he/she takes the test tests on that topic. After passing the tests successfully, he/she masters the next topics. If he/she does not get enough points on the test, he/she studies the topics again.

Let's briefly review the functions and use of the web application "Methodology for creating and implementing software that develops students' independent work activities".

Interface of the teacher's section of the web application "Methodology for creating and implementing software that develops students' independent work activities"

The main interface of the web application for students to use
Overview of the "Education" menu in the web application

CONCLUSION

Thus, in this web application, by establishing mutual communication between students, the path to the effectiveness of their independent learning is paved. In this case, it is certainly useful for the teacher not to leave the process unattended, but a little passive intervention in the process will open the way for students to exchange ideas more freely. This is especially reflected in practical exercises. That is, students solve problems related to the topic, present them to everyone, and are less worried about being found to have made mistakes. The teacher can intervene in areas where there are fundamental, substantive errors, and it has been observed that elementary errors are often corrected by other students in the group [7].

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